

PHYSICO CHEMICAL STUDIES IN THE FORMATION OF COMPLEX STANNIOXALATES. PART I. CONDUCTOMETRIC STUDY OF THE $\text{Sn}(\text{OH})_4\text{—H}_2\text{C}_2\text{O}_4$ SYSTEM

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The complex formation between stannic tin and oxalic acid has been studied by the electrical conductivity method. From the curves, evidence has been obtained for the existence of the compounds: $\text{Sn}(\text{C}_2\text{O}_4)_2$ and $\text{H}_2\text{Sn}(\text{C}_2\text{O}_4)_4$.

In several publications (Dey and Bhattacharya, *Curr. Sci.*, 1945, 14, 69; Dey, *Univ. Allahabad Studies*, 1946, 22, 7) it has been shown that the inhibition of the precipitation of stannic sulphide in presence of certain organic acids is due to complex formation between stannic tin and the carboxylic ion. The extent of such an inhibition has been quantitatively studied using different quantities of oxalic acid, oxalates (Dey and Bhattacharya, *Proc. Nat. Acad. Sci. India*, 1946, 13, 86) and soluble tartrates (Dey, *ibid.*, 1947, 16, 27). The present study has been undertaken with a view to elucidating the composition of the complexes formed in a mixture of solutions of stannic tin and oxalates and this paper records the experimental results obtained by the conductometric study of stannic hydroxide-oxalic acid system.

EXPERIMENTAL

Since a solution of stannic chloride was made in hydrochloric acid to prevent hydrolysis, the solution was extremely conducting. With the experimental arrangement at our disposal it was not possible to detect minute changes in conductivity. Therefore it was thought proper to use a suspension of stannic hydroxide instead of stannic chloride solution. A concentrated solution of stannic chloride was prepared by dissolving about 50 g. of Schuchardt's stannic chloride crystals in water, acidulated with hydrochloric acid. Stannic hydroxide was precipitated from this solution by the gradual addition of a slight excess of a diluted solution of Merck's ammonia. The precipitate was washed with cold water and finally filtered through a Buchner's flask and washed thoroughly till free from electrolytes. It was then transferred to a Jena bottle, made up to a litre and shaken vigorously to obtain a homogeneous suspension. Ten c.c. of this suspension were delivered in several silica crucibles, evaporated and finally heated strongly till the weights of the residue in all the cases were constant, ensuring the homogeneity of the suspension and also the concentration.

For conductivity measurements a high degree of accuracy was maintained. Rowland's roller bridge was used and the induction coil was actuated by a lead accumulator giving not less than 2 volts. The conductivity cell was kept immersed in a thermostat maintaining a constant temperature of $20 \pm 0.1^\circ$.

In determining the cell constant, account was taken for the disuniformity of the bridge wire and the bridge was calibrated with respect to the cell constant. The method for the calibration was the modified method of Wark (*J. Phys. Chem.*, 1930, 34, 835).

as adopted by Ghosh and Jha (*J. Indian Chem. Soc.*, 1945, 22, 275). In all calculations the value of the calibration constant was used for the cell constant at various positions of the bridge wire. For the values for cell constant obtained at different positions of the bridge wire a graph was plotted and the value for the constant at any intermediate position on the wire was read from the calibration curve.

Standard solutions of oxalic acid were prepared using 'AnalaR' sample and double distilled conductivity water. Specific conductance values for different concentrations of oxalic acid solutions were determined. The values are given in Table I.

TABLE I

Electrical conductivity of oxalic acid at different dilutions.

Conc.	...	M/80	M/72	M/64	M/56	M/48	M/40	M/36	M/32	M/28
Conductivity (in 10^{-3} mhos)	...	3.833	4.146	4.704	5.186	6.011	6.982	7.551	8.265	9.343
Conc.	...	M/24	M/20	M/16	M/12	M/10	M/8	M/6	M/4	
Conductivity (in 10^{-3} mhos)	...	10.416	12.115	13.526	16.653	19.801	23.002	27.655	38.075	

Now, to a measured volume of the homogeneous stannic hydroxide suspension was added an equal volume of oxalic acid solution and the mixture was maintained at 20° for half an hour with occasional stirring. Several such mixtures were taken using different concentration of oxalic acid. After keeping at constant temperature, the conductivity of the supernatant liquids (where dissolution was not complete) or the clear solutions was determined. The results are presented in the following table.

TABLE II

Electrical conductivity of mixtures of stannic hydroxide and oxalic acid of various compositions.

Conc. of stannic hydroxide suspension = 0.8969 g. mol./litre.

Final conc. of oxalic acid in the mixture.	Ratio. total Sn : oxalic acid in the system.	Obs. conductivity of the mixture in 10^{-3} mhos.	Final conc of oxalic acid in the mixture.	Ratio of total Sn : oxalic acid in the system.	Obs. conductivity of the mixture in 10^{-3} mhos.
M/80	1 : 0.28	1.043	M/24	1 : 0.92	7.763
M/72	1 : 0.32	1.244	M/20	1 : 1.12	9.524
M/64	1 : 0.36	1.624	M/16	1 : 1.40	12.444
M/56	1 : 0.40	2.024	M/12	1 : 1.86	15.513
M/48	1 : 0.46	2.654	M/10	1 : 2.24	19.122
M/40	1 : 0.56	3.682	M/8	1 : 2.78	23.373
M/36	1 : 0.62	4.362	M/6	1 : 3.72	29.680
M/32	1 : 0.70	5.052	M/4	1 : 5.58	37.418
M/28	1 : 0.80	6.163			

DISCUSSION

The electrical conductivity results, as recorded in the preceding tables, are able to identify complex ions in a solution of stannic ions in oxalic acid, as found from the fact that the specific conductivity of the mixtures are not equal to the sum of those for the constituents. In the table below the percentage change in conductivity due to complex formation has been shown. In the cases where small quantities of oxalic acid are used, the hydroxide does not dissolve. So the ratio $\text{Sn} : \text{C}_2\text{O}_4$ refers to the total Sn in the system. These data are incorporated to give an idea of adsorption of oxalic acid by the hydroxide.

TABLE III

Changes in conductivity due to complex formation.

Ratio $\text{Sn}^{IV} : \text{C}_2\text{O}_4^{2-}$.	Conductivity of oxalic acid in 10^{-3} mhos.	Conductivity of mixture in 10^{-3} mhos.	Difference in 10^{-3} mhos.	Percentage difference.
1 : 0.28	3.833	1.043	-2.790	-72.78
1 : 0.32	4.146	1.244	-2.902	-69.98
1 : 0.36	4.704	1.624	-3.080	-65.46
1 : 0.40	5.186	2.024	-3.162	-60.98
1 : 0.46	6.011	2.654	-3.357	-55.84
1 : 0.56	6.982	3.682	-3.300	-47.26
1 : 0.62	7.554	4.352	-3.192	-42.25
1 : 0.70	8.265	5.052	-3.213	-38.86
1 : 0.80	9.343	6.163	-3.180	-34.07
1 : 0.92	10.416	7.763	-2.653	-25.45
1 : 1.12	12.116	9.524	-2.592	-20.57
1 : 1.40	13.525	12.444	-1.081	-7.99
1 : 1.86	16.653	15.518	-1.135	-6.80
1 : 2.24	19.801	19.122	-0.679	-3.43
1 : 2.78	23.002	23.373	+0.371	+1.13
1 : 3.72	27.655	29.680	+2.025	+7.32
1 : 5.58	38.075	37.418	-0.657	-1.73

A perusal of the graph showing the change in percentage difference of conductivity with the composition of the mixture will make it clear that with lower amounts of oxalic acid there is a marked decrease in electrical conductivity. It has been found by performing some experiments that stannic hydroxide, when freshly precipitated, adsorbs oxalic acid to an appreciable extent. Further, it is well known that oxalic acid peptises stannic hydroxide to the colloidal state. Dhar and co-workers (various papers in *J. Phys. Chem.*, 1925-30) have repeatedly emphasized that adsorption often precedes a chemical reaction and therefore it is evident that prior to complex formation a colloid is apt to form by the action of oxalic acid on stannic hydroxide. Hence, the conductivity values for mixtures naturally are diminished markedly when adsorption is predominant,

FIG. 1

Sn(OH)₄-H₂C₂O₄ system.

especially when lower concentrations of oxalic acid have been used. The difference now goes on diminishing as the quantity of oxalic acid is increased : this occurs with progressive formation of the compounds. The first break in the curve occurs at the ratio $\text{Sn}^{IV} : \text{C}_2\text{O}_4 = 1 : 2$, i.e. the compound $\text{Sn}(\text{C}_2\text{O}_4)_2$ is formed at this stage. The second break, a maximum in the curve, shows the existence of the complex compound $\text{H}_4\text{Sn}(\text{C}_2\text{O}_4)_4$. These results therefore lead us to the conclusion that besides the formation of normal stannic oxalate, only one compound, a complex one, is formed by the reaction between stannic hydroxide and oxalic acid. It is interesting to observe that various earlier workers (vide Dey and Bhattacharya, *loc. cit.*) isolated complex compounds by crystallisation of mixtures of stannic chloride and organic acids. The compositions reached by them by chemical analysis seem to be those for double salts or adsorption compounds rather than true complexes. We are therefore of opinion, that in addition to ordinary chemical methods, physico-chemical methods must be adopted in order to get an idea of the composition of complex compounds.

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Received June 24, 1948.